

THE IMPACT OF SPORTS PARTICIPATION UPON STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC CREATIVITIES: MEDIATING ROLE OF IMAGERY ABILITY & PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of sports participation on the students' motivation and academic creativities via mediating roles of imagery ability and psychological capital. In an increasingly competitive academic environment, recognizing the factors that enhance intrinsic motivation and creative thinking amid students has become essential. Thus, drawing upon theories of embodied cognition and positive psychology, research investigates how engagement in physical activities subsidizes to emotional and cognitive resources that foster the academic development. The study postulates that the students who regularly participate in sports validate heightened creativity and motivation due to enhanced psychological visualization skills (imagery ability) and strengthened psychological resources like hope, self-efficacy, resilience and optimism (psychological capital) in the particular context. The sports offer unstructured and structured opportunities to develop imagination, discipline, and problem-solving skills that are transferable to academic contexts. Through physical engagement, students build stronger mental frameworks for visualizing goals, planning tasks, and generating novel ideas, all of which are essential components of academic creativity. The current study was based upon some assumptions aimed to chase through different methods and procedures towards desired leading conclusion to extract the required information and make suitable decisions about the research variables. The primary data was collected from the students hailing from higher education institutions, Punjab, Pakistan. The mediation models were applied to test the indirect effects of imagery ability and psychological capital on relationship between sports participation and academic outcomes. The findings reveal that both mediators play significant roles, sports participants tend to have higher imagery ability which enhances their capacity and skills to engage in creative academic thinking. Simultaneously, sports foster psychological capital, which drives academic motivation and perseverance. The dual mediation effects underscore a multidimensional pathway through that physical activity supports motivational and intellectual development. This study contributes to the broader understanding that how sports, traditionally viewed as a means for physical health, also influence cognitive and psychological constructs essential for the academic achievement. It suggests that the educational institutions should view sports as the integral component of student development, not only for physical well-being but also for cultivating creativity, motivation, and psychological resilience. The findings advocate for the curriculum models that incorporate sports and spiritual training to holistically support students' innovation potential and academic success with some recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary era, the physical activities and sports participation have long been recognized for their positive effects on physical health, but their influence extends beyond the realm of the physical transformation. Gradually, research suggests that engagement in sports can intensely impact various aspects of students' lives, including their motivation and academic creativity [1]. The motivation is critical factor in determining students' engagement and success in academics, while intrinsic motivation, driven by internal factors like interest and enjoyment, and ideally, extrinsic motivators like grades and external rewards play a significant role [2]. Thus, the sports participation has been linked to both types of motivation, providing students with prospects to pursue activities and find them personally rewarding while offering extrinsic rewards like team victories/individual successes.

Engagement in sports fosters a sense of competence and mastery as students strive to improve their skills and compete against themselves and others. This sense of competence can spill over into academic domain, bolstering students' belief and confidence in their abilities to overcome challenges [3]. Besides, the camaraderie and social connections forged through team sports can enhance students' sense of belonging and intrinsic motivation, leading to increased effort and persistence in academic endeavors [4]. The creativity is a multifaceted construct encompassing the ability to generate novel ideas, think divergently, and solve problems creatively [5], while traditionally linked with the arts and humanities, creativity is equally vital in academic pursuits across all disciplines. The engagement in sports can stimulate creativity and innovation through innumerable mechanisms.

The sports participation provides students with opportunities for experiential learning, where they must adapt to changing situations, think on their feet, and devise strategies to achieve their desired goals [6]. This dynamic environment fosters cognitive flexibility and problem-solving skills, essential components of academic creativity leading towards academic success culminates at successful academic careers [7]. Moreover, the collaborative nature of team sports cultivates interpersonal skills and teamwork, fostering environment where students learn to communicate effectively, negotiate differences, and leverage each other's strengths for different outcomes [8]. In this linking, these interpersonal dynamics mirror the collaborative processes seen in creative endeavors, where diverse viewpoints and ideas converge to produce innovative solutions toward the desired consequences.

The physical activity has been shown to boost cognitive function, including memory, attention, and executive function, which are vital for academic creativity as regular exercise promotes brain ability to reorganize and form new connections, that enhance cognitive flexibility and capacity for creative thinking [9]. The sports participation has reflective impact on students' motivation and academic creativity as by fostering the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, sports provide students with drive and determination to excel in diverse situations and contexts [10]. Moreover, engagement in sports cultivates the cognitive and interpersonal skills necessary for academic creativity, laying the foundation for innovative thinking and problem-solving [11]. Thus, there is a need to recognize valuable role of sports participation in enhancing motivation and fostering creativity among students. In the contemporary environments, there has been growing interest in exploring the multifaceted relationship amid sports participation, the students' motivation, academic creativity, and imagery ability, and thus understanding how these factors intersect can provides the valuable insights into enhancing students' overall development and academic success is significant tasks from various dimensions [12]. The sports participation has long been recognized as a powerful motivator for students as engaging in sports provides prospects for students to set goals, strive for excellence,

and experience satisfaction of achievement [13]. Moreover, sports involvement fosters a sense of belonging and camaraderie, which enhances students' motivation by providing social support and reinforcing the positive social identities [14], and linked to incentivize students to excel both in the sports and academics.

The academic creativity includes the ability to think critically, solve problems innovatively, and generate novel ideas across various academic disciplines whereas creativity is linked with the desirability to produce innovative outcomes [15]. Thus, the sports participation can contribute to academic creativity, cognitive skills and strategies developed over sports, such as goal-setting, strategic planning, and adaptability, are convenient to academic contexts [16]. Furthermore, the collaborative nature of team sports fosters interpersonal skills and teamwork, which are vital for brainstorming and cooperating on creative tasks [17]. The physical activity is shown to enhance cognitive function, including divergent thinking that is key element of creativity and promote neuroplasticity and increases blood flow to the brain, thereby facilitating creative thinking over the imagery capabilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The linkages in sports participation, students' motivation, academic creativity, imagery ability, and psychological capital are complex and multifaceted, representing a dynamic interplay amid physical activity, cognitive processes, and psychological resources and thus understanding these linkages requires examining how each factor influences and interact with the others. The sports participation serves as a source of motivation for students, fostering a sense of purpose, success, and social connection [28]. The engagement in sports enhance intrinsic motivation by providing opportunities for personal growth, skill development and enjoyment that are crucial in attaining desired outcomes [29]. Thus, experiencing success in sports, such as achieving personal bests, increase students' self-efficacy beliefs and confidence, motivating them to excel in both athletic and academic pursuits.

The sports participation fosters cognitive skills and strategies that are transferable to academic contexts, such as problem-solving, decision-making, and creative thinking as engaging in sports fosters growth mindset, encouraging student to embrace challenges, persevere through setbacks, and explore innovative solutions [30]. Thus, the collaborative nature of team sports promotes communication, teamwork, and cooperation, which are vital for generating and implementing creative ideas in academic settings [31]. Sports often involve mental imagery techniques, such as visualization and mental rehearsal, to enhance performance and skill acquisition [32]. Engaging in sports provides chances for students to develop and refine their imagery ability by practicing visualization of movements, strategies, and sports scenarios thereby increase confidence in their abilities and outcomes.

The interdisciplinary literature has examined the impact of sports participation on wide ranging academic and psychological outcomes in students as sports participation is linked with physical health, is gradually recognized for its impact on students' psychological resources and cognitive abilities [11]. The underlying rationale is that sports demand the self-discipline, goal-setting, and persistence, that transfer into academic settings where students persist over challenges, maintain focus, and strive toward success [14]. This transmission is alleged to occur not only behaviorally, but over emotional and cognitive mechanisms. Among cognitive mediators, imagery ability has gained particular attention [17], in sports science, educational psychology, as well as cognitive development have explored how engagement in structured physical activity influences intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

The students engage in visualization and mental rehearsal, that boosts their skills and capacity to anticipate, plan, and respond creatively to challenges along with capacity to emotionally pretend strategies, actions, and outcomes, is cultivated over sports practice [21]. The literature supports view that students with higher imagery ability tend to validate greater academic creativity since they are better equipped to form complex associations and explore novel options in their thinking [24]. The psychological capital emerges as the vital motivational and emotional mediator in the relationship amid sports participation and academic outcomes [27]. The psychological capital the construct comprising optimism, self-efficacy, courage, and resilience is developed over sustained sports engagement students in creating the ideas, picturing multiple solutions to problems, and planning academic tasks.

These elements collectively boost students' psychological readiness to take initiative in academic work and sustain creative efforts even in uncertain and hard conditions [30]. The research shows that students with high psychological capital are more likely to exhibit the intrinsic motivation, risk-taking, and persistence, all critical components of both creativity and academic performance [33]. The participation in sports cultivates confidence in one's abilities, encourages goal-directed behavior, fosters positive outlooks in the face of challenges and promotes the emotional recovery from setbacks. Thus, motivation fuels the willingness to engage in cognitive exploration, while reinforces creativity motivation by making learning satisfying and personally meaningful [36]. The literature further highlights the reciprocal relationship between motivation and creativity in academic leading domains.

The studies suggest that sports can offer psychological and social scaffolding, providing students with environments that support competence, autonomy, and relatedness factors central to self-determination theory, explains arrival of sovereign creativity and motivation [37]. The literature supports a comprehensive model over which sports participation influences students' academic creativity and motivation through mediating pathways of greater imagery ability and emotional resilience [12]. These mediators operate in in diverse situations, as imagery ability supports the problem-solving and cognitive flexibility, while psychological capital nurtures emotional solidity and sureness required to pursue creative philosophies [7]. The sports participation, by increasing psychological capital and imagery capability, that acts as the foundational activity that promotes indirectly this feedback loop.

The sports participation serves as complex developmental tool that stimulates the psychological and cognitive circumstances necessary for academic creativity and motivation [11]. The model reflects the shift in modern educational research toward all-inclusive approaches that recognize the role of physical activity not just as health intervention, but as a contributor to emotional and intellectual development [15]. These findings offer strong support for educational strategies that integrate psychological, physical, and cognitive advance as part of inclusive approach to student success [17]. By developing the students' capacity to plan, imagine, and remain bright, sports engagement has potential to significantly enhance their educational experience and performance, sports engagement contributes to student academic lives by fostering the essential psychological and intellectual traits.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature with experimental that aims to examine relationship in chasing the hypotheses and reaching conclusion. The positivism approach was used to chasing relationships among research variables (food, dietary habits, and exercise) of study. The research approach specifies the way through which data is collected from the respondents by retrieving them to reach their answers about variables of research in order to reach required conclusion through justification towards desired outcomes. The population of interest in this

research is students hailing from colleges in Punjab, Pakistan wherein 2890 students from colleges wherein a sample is drawn from population, has been extracted by using the sampling formula widely used in the social research studies. Thus, 351 questionnaires were distributed among which 340 were recollected and used for analysis. Similarly, the random simple technique was used to access the population of study which comes under the non-probability technique to ensure required data from diverse dimensions. Also, both secondary and primary data were used to collect data from respondents and from existing knowledge databased to analyze data to reach conclusion. The questionnaires were adopted from previous studies. Similarly, 5-point Likert scale was used to record responses of respondents about research issues in particular context to access respondents and achieving desired outcomes.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Sports Participation	334	1.30	4.80	3.2883	.73749
Imagery Ability	334	1.33	4.67	3.1861	.82803
Psychological Capital	334	1.70	4.70	3.3790	.67804
Students' Motivation	334	1.60	4.60	3.5023	.65649
Academic Creativities	334	1.63	4.70	3.4041	.61483
Valid N (List-Wise)	334				

The descriptive statistics provides significant information in describing the research issues from different perspectives like mean, minimum and maximum responses rate in respondent responses toward the research variables like the sports participation, imagery ability, psychological capital, students' motivation and academic creativities, along with mean and standard deviation wherein the results provide significant information in descriptive statistics table for measuring variables in particular perspectives.

H1: There is positive association amid sports participation, imagery ability, psychological capital, students' motivation & academic creativities (H1).

Correlations Analysis

		[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Sports Participation [1]	Pearson Correlation	1	.173**	.404**	.461**	.601**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.000	.000	.000
	N	334	334	334	334	334
Imagery Ability [2]	Pearson Correlation	.173**	1	.141*	.054	.219**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		.010	.327	.000
	N	334	334	334	334	334
Psychological Capital [3]	Pearson Correlation	.404**	.141*	1	.402**	.449**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.010		.000	.000
	N	334	334	334	334	334
Students' Motivation [4]	Pearson Correlation	.461**	.054	.402**	1	.496**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.327	.000		.000
	N	334	334	334	334	334
Academic Creativities [5]	Pearson Correlation	.601**	.219**	.449**	.496**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	334	334	334	334	334

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation procedure was used to examine association among sports participation, imagery ability, psychological capital, students' motivation and academic creativities with respect to the strength and direction in relationships in particular context to reach the desired conclusion about the hypothesized association. The results of current study through correlation confirmed desired association wherein significant association is evident among research variables of current study like sports participation and students' motivation ($R = .461$ & $P = .000$), sports participation and academic creativities ($R = .61$ & $P = .000$) imagery ability and students' motivation ($R = .054$ & $P = .327$), imagery ability and academic creativities ($R = .219$ & $P = .000$), psychological capital and students' motivation ($R = .402$ & $P = .000$), psychological capital and academic creativities ($R = .449$ & $P = .000$), and imagery ability and psychological capital ($R = .404$ & $P = .000$), and hypothesis is accepted.

H2: There is a positive impact of the sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital on students' motivation (H2).

Regression Analysis (Model Summary)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.520a	.270	.263	.56346

Regression Analysis (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.742	3	12.914	40.675	.000b
	Residual	104.773	330	.317		
	Total	143.514	333			

Regression Analysis (Coefficients)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.699	.198		8.576	.000
	Sports Participation	.323	.046	.363	6.996	.000
	Imagery Ability	-.036	.038	-.046	-.958	.339
	Psychological Capital	.254	.050	.262	5.085	.000

a. Predictors: Sports Participation, Psychological Capital and Imagery Ability,

b. Dependent Variable: Students' Motivation

The regression procedure was used to examine the cause-&-effect relationships among research variables of study like sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital on students' motivation in order to confirm the prediction of students' motivation. The results of regression confirmed that existence of prediction wherein 27% change is evident in students' motivation is due to sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital with the significant impact like sports participation (coefficient value = .323 & P-value = .000), imagery ability (coefficient value = -.036 & P-value = .339), and psychological capital (coefficient value = .254 & P-value = .000), and hypothesis was partially accepted.

H3: There is a positive impact of the sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital on academic creativities (H3).

Regression Analysis (Model Summary)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R2	SEE
1	.650a	.422	.417	.46952

Regression Analysis (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	53.133	3	17.711	80.341	.000b
	Residual	72.747	330	.220		
	Total	125.880	333			

Regression Analysis (Coefficients)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.100	.165		6.661	.000
	Sports Participation	.407	.038	.488	10.582	.000
	Imagery Ability	.075	.032	.101	2.371	.018
	Psychological Capital	.215	.042	.237	5.176	.000

a. Predictors: Sports Participation, Psychological Capital and Imagery Ability

b. Dependent Variable: Academic Creativities

The regression procedure was used to examine the cause-&effect relationships among research variables of study like sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital on students' motivation in order to confirm the prediction of academic creativities. The results of regression confirmed that existence of prediction wherein 42.2% change is evident in academic creativities is due to sports participation, imagery ability and psychological capital with significant impact like sports participation (coefficient value = .407 & P-value = .000), imagery ability (coefficient value = .075 & P-value = .018), and psychological capital (coefficient value = .215 & P-value = .000), and hypothesis was accepted.

H4: There is significant mediating role of imagery ability in linking the sports participation and students' motivation (H4).

Mediation First Step (a)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.1730	.0299	.6671	11.3870	1.0000	332.0000	.0008

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.5473	.1860	13.6985	.0000	2.1815	2.9131
Sports Participation	.1943	.0576	3.3745	.0008	.0810	.3075

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation

Criterion Variable: Imagery Ability

Mediation Second & Third Steps (b & c')

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4613	.2128	.3413	33.5616	2.0000	331.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.2083	.1992	11.0876	.0000	1.8165	2.6001
Imagery Ability	-.0212	.0377	-.5628	.5740	-.0953	.0529
Sports Participation	.4140	.0506	8.1882	.0000	.3146	.5135

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation, Imagery Ability

Criterion Variable: Students' Motivation

Mediation Fourth Step (c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4605	.2121	.3406	65.4151	1.0000	332.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1543	.1651	13.0466	.0000	1.8295	2.4792
Sports Participation	.4099	.0507	8.0880	.0000	.3102	.5096

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation

Criterion Variable: Students' Motivation

The mediation analysis was used to examine the mediating role of imagery ability in linking the sports participation and students' motivation over different paths that are mandatory in process in order to ensure the direct and indirect relationships among the variables of different nature from different dimensions in reaching the conclusion. All the mediation paths (a, b, c & \hat{c}), provides the important information regarding the direct and indirect relationships through coefficient and p-values which are significant and confirmed the partial mediation role of imagery ability in linking the sports participation and students' motivation due to main decision about the decrease in coefficient value form (.4099) in direct relationship to (.4144) in indirect relationship while the significant values remained important in the entire mediation process and thus hypothesis was partially accepted in study.

H5: There is significant mediating role of imagery ability in linking the sports participation and academic creativities (H5).

Mediation First Step (a)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.1730	.0299	.6671	11.3870	1.0000	332.0000	.0008

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.5473	.1860	13.6985	.0000	2.1815	2.9131
Sports Participation	.1943	.0576	3.3745	.0008	.0810	.3075

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation

Criterion Variable: Imagery Ability

Mediation Second & Third Steps (b & \hat{c})

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6125	.3752	.2376	118.9154	2.0000	331.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5317	.1335	11.4703	.0000	1.2690	1.7944
Imagery Ability	.0879	.0336	2.6152	.0093	.0218	.1541
Sports Participation	.4842	.0376	12.8699	.0000	.4102	.5582

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation, Imagery Ability

Criterion Variable: Academic Creativities

Mediation Fourth Step (c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6013	.3616	.2421	194.0227	1.0000	332.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	Se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.7557	.1236	14.2060	.0000	1.5125	1.9988
Sports Participation	.5013	.0360	13.9292	.0000	.4305	.5721

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation

Criterion Variable: Academic Creativities

The mediation analysis was used to examine mediating role of academic creativities in linking sports participation and Academic Creativities over different paths that are mandatory in process in order to ensure direct and indirect relationships among the variables of different nature from different dimensions in reaching the conclusion. All the mediation paths (a, b, c & \hat{c}), provides the important information regarding the direct and indirection relationships through coefficient and p-values which are significant and confirmed partial mediation role of academic creativities in linking the sports participation and students' motivation due to main decision about decrease in coefficient value form (.5013) in direct relationship to (.4842) in indirect relationship while the significant values remained important in entire mediation process and thus hypothesis was partially accepted in study.

DISCUSSION

In contemporary era, the physical activities and sports participation have long been recognized for their positive effects on physical health, but their influence extends beyond the realm of the physical transformation. Gradually, research suggests that engagement in sports can intensely impact various aspects of students' lives, including their motivation and academic creativity [1]. The motivation is critical factor in determining students' engagement and success in academics, while intrinsic motivation, driven by internal factors like interest and enjoyment, and ideally, extrinsic motivators like grades and external rewards play a significant role [2]. Thus, the sports participation has been linked to both types of motivation, providing students with prospects to pursue activities and find them personally rewarding while offering extrinsic rewards like team victories/individual successes.

The physical activity has been shown to boost cognitive function, including memory, attention, and executive function, which are vital for academic creativity as regular exercise promotes brain ability to reorganize and form new connections, that enhance cognitive flexibility and capacity for creative thinking [9]. The sports participation has reflective impact on students' motivation and academic creativity as by fostering the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, sports provide students with drive and determination to excel in diverse situations and contexts [10]. Moreover, engagement in sports cultivates the cognitive and interpersonal skills necessary for academic creativity, laying the foundation for innovative thinking and problem-solving [11]. Thus, there is a need to recognize valuable role of sports participation in enhancing motivation and fostering creativity among students.

The academic creativity includes the ability to think critically, solve problems innovatively, and generate novel ideas across various academic disciplines whereas creativity is linked with the

desirability to produce innovative outcomes [15]. Thus, the sports participation can contribute to academic creativity, cognitive skills and strategies developed over sports, such as goal-setting, strategic planning, and adaptability, are convenient to academic contexts [16]. Furthermore, the collaborative nature of team sports fosters interpersonal skills and teamwork, which are vital for brainstorming and cooperating on creative tasks [17]. The physical activity is shown to enhance cognitive function, including divergent thinking that is key element of creativity and promote neuroplasticity and increases blood flow to the brain, thereby facilitating creative thinking over the imagery capabilities.

The sports participation fosters cognitive skills and strategies that are transferable to academic contexts, such as problem-solving, decision-making, and creative thinking as engaging in sports fosters growth mindset, encouraging student to embrace challenges, persevere through setbacks, and explore innovative solutions [30]. Thus, the collaborative nature of team sports promotes communication, teamwork, and cooperation, which are vital for generating and implementing creative ideas in academic settings [31]. Sports often involve mental imagery techniques, such as visualization and mental rehearsal, to enhance performance and skill acquisition [32]. Engaging in sports provides chances for students to develop and refine their imagery ability by practicing visualization of movements, strategies, and sports scenarios thereby increase confidence in their abilities and outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The educational programs may include mental imagery exercises to strengthen students' goal-setting strategies and creative thinking that may further helps in attaining the leading and desired consequences.
2. The Institutions should incorporate regular and structured sports activities to enhance the students' engagement and motivation in academic tasks overwhelmed at desired output culminates at anticipated success.
3. The teachers, sports coaches, and counselors should work together to create a balanced approach that supports both academic and physical development from diverse dimensions leading to the desired developments.
4. The institutions should implement workshops and support systems that foster students' resilience, self-efficacy, optimism, and hope that are considered as critical dimensions for desired leading consequences.

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